

THE CONFLICTS USED IN THE NOVEL THE RELUCTANT FUNDAMENTALIST

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Annotation: It is a truism bordering on a tautology that first-person novels are all about voice, but seldom can that observation have been more apposite than in the case of Mohsin Hamid's *The Reluctant Fundamentalist*. We learn that Changez is a highly educated Pakistani who worked as a financial analyst for a prestigious firm in New York.

Key words: literature, education, story, books, study, Pakistani, writer, company, love, school, university, America.

Mohsin Hamid was born on 23 July 1971. He was born in Lahore, Pakistan. Mohsin Hamid was born on 23 July 1971. He was born into a Punjabi family and they basically belong to Kashmir. Much of his childhood can be traced to the United States. His father was a professor. Hamid's father was enrolled in Ph.D. at Stanford university. Mohsin Hamid had to stay from 3-9 years of age in the United States with his family. After some time, his family came back to Pakistan. Hamid pursued his early education in Pakistan in Lahore American School. When he reached the age of 18, he returned to the United States in order to get a higher education. Mohsin Hamid got admission to Princeton university. He is a Pakistani writer. His most famous works are *Reluctant Fundamentalist*, *Moth Smoke*, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*. Mohsin Hamid is a Pakistani born English novelist. He was born in Lahore, Pakistan.

The Reluctant Fundamentalist, like much of Hamid's writing is obsessed with the image of a Muslim man's beard and how this could signal latent danger or radical conservatism. True, Hamid's writing is at times self-reflexive on this point, but this is usually not the case. In his first novel *Moth Smoke*, for example, the main character Daru sits alone in the cinema when a man approaches, prompting Hamid's protagonist to immediately note his 'thick black beard'. Predictably, this man turns out to be a "fundo" just as a Daru had expected from the moment saw him. Mohsin Hamid has been known as a water lily for the manner in which he's floated here and there. The 43-year-old writer from Lahore has built up roots, developed and flourished in places as unique as Pakistan, London, California and New York. He's most popular as the writer of the 2007 universal smash hit *The Reluctant Fundamentalist* which has been translated in 30 unique dialects. This novel was shortlisted for Britain's Man Booker Prize. This was made into a 2013 film coordinated by Mira Nair. Hamid's professional life started in the business world, not in book composing. In the wake of the to Princeton university and Harvard Law School, he filled in as an administration expert in the New York. His first novel *Moth Smoke* in 2000, propelled him into the literary limelight. The narrative of a financier in Lahore, *Moth Smoke* was a finalist for the PEN/Hemingway grant, given for an

extraordinary presentation work of fiction. Hamid proceeded to write two additional books and in the long run, left New York for Lahore. He lives with his wife and two kids. His new book of articles, *Discount and its Civilizations: Dispatches from Lahore, New York and London*, investigates a portion of the his reasoning, reflection and memory in the course of recent years.

In 2010, the Uk magazine *Granta* published its only Pakistan issue. The magazine's cover was decorated by an artist from Karachi, Islam Gull, and celebrated a Pakistan that seldom travels far from our borders. There were no explosions, beards or ominous men with guns at their back, but only natural scenes of lakes, tigers and birds. Flipping through, one could have been impressed. The contributors were diverse enough- 19 in all- with a good mix of " international " and " local " voices. A flaw, if there was one, was never particularly noticeable: out of the 18 pieces of poetry, fiction and reportage, just three had been written in local languages. Admittedly, Pakistanis writing in English have had it good for almost two decades now, long before the 2010 issue of *Granta* was produced. However, surprising though it may now seem, English literature classroom have historically not wandered outside the boundaries of British or American writing and certainly not in any substantial way before the 1970s. If Pakistani literature in English now has some global importance, this happened very much within living memory- with the creation of a World literature canon starting in the 1960s, the setting up of postcolonial studies as an academic discipline in the 1980s and the collapse of the twin towers in 2001. Of the present crop of renowned Pakistani writers in English, most of whom came of age in the early to-mid 2000s, Mohsin Hamid is perhaps the most famous.

He started a job in McKinley and company in New York to support his student life. He was appointed as a management consultant. In order to complete his novel, he took some vacations. Afterwards, in 2001, he went to London. He planned to spend a year in London but he spent eight years there. He got the citizenship of the United Kingdom in 2006 and became a dual citizen of Pakistan and the United Kingdom. Hamid's wife is also from Lahore. She got educated abroad. After marriage, Hamid's love for traveling increased. His drifting from country to the country made him famous with the name of water lily. He moved to Pakistan in 2009 with his wife Zahra and daughter Dina. His life is mostly divided into different parts of the world such as Lahore, London, New York, Greece and Italy.

Hamid is perhaps entitled to write the fiction he sees fit and to tackle the issues he values. And yet, it is also unethical to ignore that to be read outside our borders is a privilege to which only certain writers have access. A look at the Pakistani *Granta* is proof enough: most of the writers published and even the few translators present are those educated and based abroad or who have at least spent more than a significant portion of the their lives in Europe or North America. The point here is power: the individual merits or demerits of English writers notwithstanding, it is really not debatable that they benefit from their

generally upper or upper-middle-class status, which allows them to travel to and enter Western language publishing systems directly to forge connections that help their name and work spread farther and wider. There is also the question of influence: it is unreasonable to assume that elite education and extended stays abroad do not shape one's outlook or art. Like Hamid, many of Pakistan's internationally renowned authors bear the stamp of their experiences in the stories they choose to tell, who the stories are about the kinds of characters they create and in what for them, counts as real conflict and not 'ideology'. The Pakistani Granta reflects this bias too, as a disproportionate number of stories are standard fare: immigrants abroad, Islamic violence and the antagonism between tradition and modernity. Contrary to what a certain brand of intellectuals may argue, Pakistan and its people look very different in its many local languages, which cannot be subsumed by English. This is not parochialism, but an acknowledgement of how the diversity of class, caste, kinship and religious viewpoints shape the texture and value-systems of the languages people have grown up speaking. People's values and their social and historical experience give meaning to their language.

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